

Supporting Information

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Chitosan Composite Membrane with Efficient Hydroxide Ion Transport via Nano-Confined Hydrogen Bonding Network for Alkaline Zinc-Based Flow Batteries

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Figure S1. The surface morphology of the PES/PVP substrate.

Figure S2. The scheme illustration of preparation process of the designed Cts-Cu-M.

Figure S3. The cross-section morphology of the Cts-Cu-M of different magnifications.

Figure S4. The N1s XPS spectra of the (a) Cts-Cu-M and (b) PES/PVP membrane.

Figure S5. The magnified FTIR spectra of prepared membranes.

Figure S6. The hexagonal nanochannels of Cts-Cu-M.

Figure S7. The zeta potential values of Cts-Cu-M at PH=7.

Figure S8. The hydroxide ion transference numbers through different membranes calculated from the current-voltage (I-V) profiles.

Figure S9. The contact angle result of prepared Cts-Cu-M under 3M NaOH solution.

Figure S10. The corresponding models of different perspectives of nano-confined channels for simulating the OH⁻ transport during the AIMD simulation.

Figure S11. The snapshots extracted from the AIMD simulation, revealing the OH^- transport within Cts-Cu-M.

Figure S12. The energy barrier of proton transfer for (a) uncrosslinked chitosan matrix and (b) Cu²⁺ cross-linked nano-confined channels of Cts-Cu-M.

Figure S13. The AZIFB performance assembled with Nafion 212 at different current densities.

Figure S14. (a) The cycling performance of AZIFB assembled with PES/PVP at the current density of 80 mA cm^{-2} , and (b) corresponding discharge capacity and discharge energy for each cycle at 80 mA cm^{-2} .

Figure S15. The SEM morphology of Cts-Cu-M after 200 cycles of cycling at the current density of 200 mA cm⁻².

Figure S16. The cross-section morphology of Cts-Cu-M after 200 cycles of cycling at the current density of 200 mA cm^{-2} .

Figure S 17. The XPS characterization of Cts-Cu-M-Cycled membrane surface.

Figure S18. The polarization curves of AZIFB at 80% SOC, 50% SOC, and 20% SOC employing (a) Cts-Cu-M membrane, and (b) PES/PVP.